

IR66 promising as a short-duration variety for the Mekong Delta

L. T. Du, N. T. N. Hue, P. C. Voc, and N. V. Luat, *Cuu Long Delta Rice Research Institute (CLRRI), Omon, Hau Giang, Vietnam*

We selected several breeding lines for yield potential and adverse soil tolerance

from the national breeding program and from 1985 IRTP nurseries.

Average yield of IR66 in CLRRI trials was the same as or higher than that of commercial check NN6A, especially in slightly acid sulfate soil (Table 1). IR66 was moderately resistant to brown planthopper biotype 2 and blast, and susceptible to bacterial blight (Table 2).

Table 1. Yield of IR66 in 1985-88 dry and wet seasons at CLRRI, Omon, Haugiang, Vietnam.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)						Average
	Dry season			Wet season			
	1985	1986	1987	1986	1987	1988	
IR66	5.5	4.8	6.1	5.7	5.8	4.8	5.5
NN6A (Check)	5.2	4.5	5.8	5.2	5.2	4.6	5.1
CV (%)	18.2	10.8	8.3	11.0	3.4	5.2	
LSD (0.05)	0.5		ns	0.9	0.3	0.6	

IR66 was advanced to adaptive research trials in farmers' fields in 1988. Good grain quality rice varieties (IR64, OM80, Nang huong, Mot bui) are grown on a large scale in export rice-growing areas. IR66 is considered another major rice variety. ■

Table 2. Reaction of IR66 to insects and diseases at CLRRI.

Variety	Reaction ^a to		
	BPH	BI	BB
IR66	3	3-5	5-7
NN6A	3	7-9	7
Resistant check ^b	3	1	2
Susceptible check	99		8

^a By the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. ^b Resistant check = IR36 for brown planthopper (BPH), IR8 for blast (BI), Composelak for bacterial blight (BB). ^c Susceptible check = TN1 for BPH, NN7A for BI, IR8 for BB.

Seed technology

Comparison of immunoradiometric assay (IRMA) and concentration inoculation (CI) in inspecting rice seed for *Xanthomonas oryzae pv. oryzicola*

Xie Guanlin, *Zhejiang Academy of Agricultural Science, Hangzhou*; and Wang Gongjin, *Jiangsu Academy of Agricultural Science, Nanjing, China*

Bacterial leaf streak caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae pv. oryzicola* is a quarantined plant disease in China. Inspection is

very important when seeds are transported within the country.

We compared the efficiency of IRMA with that of CI for testing seed.

IRMA had many advantages over CI: It has greater sensitivity and accuracy and is faster (see table). It took only 4 h to test one batch of samples for bacteria. A smaller 4-g sample could be tested. The results are more stable, and less affected by environment. Seeds can be tested in the laboratory. Seed inspection by CI is often done May-Sep, because temperatures are too low in Oct-Apr. With IRMA, testing can be done anytime. ■

Comparison of IRMA and CI in seed inspection for detecting *X. c. pv. oryzicola*.

Description	IRMA	CI
Concentration needed (cells/ml)	$5 \times 10^2 - 10^3$	10^5
Time required (h)	4	98
Accuracy (%)	96	63
Sample weight (g)	4	30
Precision	High	Low
Efficiency	High	Low
Factors affecting results	Few	Many
Results	Stable	Variable
Test site	Laboratory	Field or greenhouse
Detection time	Anytime	May-Sep

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Soils

Effect of soil moisture on boron availability and uptake

J. C. Katyal and B. Singh, *All-India Coordinated Scheme of Micronutrients in Soils and Plants, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana 141004, India*

We explored the effect of changing soil moisture from aerobic (field capacity) to anaerobic (saturation or continuous

flooding) on boron (B) availability. This moisture cycle occurs in rice grown on permeable coarse-textured soils with frequent irrigation.

Porcelain pots (34 cm diameter × 29 cm height) with a leaching outlet on the side near the bottom were filled with 15 kg sandy loam soil (pH 8.6, 0.10% organic C, electrical conductance 0.30 dS/m in 1:2 soil water ratio, 0.57% CaCO₃) treated with 60, 25, 25, and 1 mg N, P, K, and B (as H₃BO₃)/kg soil.

Six 40-d-old PR106 seedlings were transplanted in each pot. Moisture treatments were continuous flooding to 5-cm depth with no leaching. Field capacity was maintained by adding water on alternate days.

Soil solution was collected by suction from all pots at 7, 14, 22, and 28 d after transplanting (DT) and pH, Eh, pCO₂, and electrical conductivity (EC) estimated. To determine B, an aliquot of the soil solution was mixed with azomethine-H in

the presence of a buffer-making reagent (this avoided interference due to Al, Cu, and Fe). The intensity of yellow color developed was read at 420 nm on a spectrophotometer.

Three rice hills from each pot were harvested 30 DT. Dry matter was recorded and 1 g samples ashed at 500 °C for 1 h were dissolved in 20 ml of 0.36 NH₂SO₄. A 2-ml aliquot of the solution was analyzed for B following the azomethine-H procedure.

High B concentration at the beginning of both water regimes declined over time. The decrease was faster and steeper in field capacity pots. At 7 DT, the soil solution extracted from the pots at field capacity had about 1.5 times higher B concentration than that extracted from the flooded pots. This trend continued for 2 wk, then reversed (see figure).

Irrespective of water regime, coefficients of correlation ($r = 0.79^{**}$) and the closely parallel changes in water soluble B and EC indicate that B closely follows EC. Coefficients of correlation between water-soluble B and pH, Eh, or r_{CO_2} were not significant.

Dry matter yield of rice in pots maintained at field capacity was about

Periodic changes in EC and concentration of B in soil solution under field capacity and under continuous flooding. Ludhiana, India.

40% less than that of rice in flooded pots (see table). Dry matter yield of continuously flooded rice was higher, and soil solution B at 15-30 DT higher, but uptake of B was lower than in rice grown under field capacity. It appears that aerobic conditions favor higher B uptake by rice than do anaerobic conditions. ■

Dry matter yield and B uptake by 30-d-old rice plants under different soil moisture conditions.

Soil moisture	Dry matter yield (g/pot)	B uptake (µg/pot)
Continuous flooding	13.2	290
Field capacity	8.2	361
S.E. (±)	0.5	10

Variation in temperature of irrigated rice soils with different drainage characteristics

L. C. Dharmasri and B. V. R. Punyawardena, Division of Soil Science, Agriculture Research Centre, Angunukolapellessa, Sri Lanka

Soil temperatures in irrigated ricefields vary with time of day. We measured soil temperature at two positions in the soil catena representing imperfectly drained and poorly drained sandy clay loam soil in an irrigated transplanted ricefield during March 1989.

Soil temperature at 5-cm depth was measured at 1-h intervals from 0700 to 1700 h for five consecutive days during the vegetative growth period, when fertilizer was scheduled to be topdressed. The imperfectly drained field was irrigated once in 4 d; the poorly drained field, once in 6 d. Temperature of the irrigation water ranged from 27.8 to

30.0 °C. Temperature of the standing water ranged from 32.2 to 34.4 °C in imperfectly drained soil and from 30.6 to 32.8 °C in poorly drained soil.

Mean daily soil temperature ranged from 26.7 to 37.5 °C in imperfectly drained soil and 26.4 to 34.7 °C in poorly drained soil (see table). The average maximum soil temperature at 5-cm depth was 35.6 ± 0.4 °C at 1500 h in imper-

fectly drained soil, and 34.1 ± 0.2 °C at 1400 h in poorly drained soil. Soil temperature increased 8.4 °C in 8 h from the nighttime minimum in imperfectly drained soil, and 7.2 °C in 7 h in poorly drained soil.

The widest temperature difference between the two soils was 1.7 °C at 1500 h. Maximum soil temperature could be measured 1400 to 1500 h. ■

Variation in soil temperature of different soil drainage classes. Angunukolapellessa, Sri Lanka.

Time (h)	Imperfectly drained soil		Poorly drained soil	
	Mean daily temperature (°C)	Temperature range (°C)	Mean daily temperature (°C)	Temperature range (°C)
0700	27.2 ± 0.2	26.7 - 28.1	26.9 ± 0.1	26.4 - 21.2
0800	27.4 ± 0.2	26.7 - 28.3	27.2 ± 0.2	26.7 - 27.8
0900	28.2 ± 0.2	27.5 - 28.9	27.7 ± 0.2	27.2 - 28.1
1000	29.4 ± 0.2	28.9 - 29.7	28.7 ± 0.2	28.1 - 29.2
1100	31.1 ± 0.2	30.6 - 31.7	30.2 ± 0.4	29.2 - 31.1
1200	32.9 ± 0.2	32.2 - 33.3	31.8 ± 0.4	30.8 - 33.3
1300	34.4 ± 0.4	33.6 - 36.4	33.1 ± 0.3	32.2 - 33.9
1400	35.4 ± 0.4	34.4 - 36.9	34.1 ± 0.2	33.6 - 34.7
1500	35.6 ± 0.4	35.0 - 37.5	33.9 ± 0.2	33.3 - 34.1
1600	35.1 ± 0.3	34.4 - 36.4	33.7 ± 0.3	32.5 - 34.4
1700	33.9 ± 0.2	33.6 - 34.7	32.9 ± 0.5	31.1 - 33.9